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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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VALORIZATION POTENTIAL OF INVASIVE MACROALGA *ASPARAGOPSIS ARMATA* FOR FOOD, FEED AND COSMECEUTICAL APPLICATIONS

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Introduction: *Asparagopsis* spp. are invasive red macroalgae of the Mediterranean with bioactive potential in food, feed, and cosmeceuticals. They provide proteins, polysaccharides, and unique halogenated metabolites, though their valorization remains limited.

Aims: This study investigated the biochemical composition of *Asparagopsis armata* and assessed its potential for sustainable applications.

Materials and Methods: Proteins were recovered by aqueous enzymatic extraction and quantified using the Kjeldahl method. Polysaccharides were isolated via water extraction and ethanol precipitation, and their concentration was measured using a UV–Vis/DMB assay. Phenolics were extracted by 70% ethanol maceration and assessed with the Folin-Ciocalteu assay. Lipids and PUFAs were extracted using the Bligh and Dyer method and analyzed with GC-MS. HS-SPME/GC-MS was used to determine volatile halogenated metabolites.

Results: *A. armata* contained high protein ($21.4 \pm 2.1\%$ w/w dw) and polysaccharide levels ($18.7 \pm 1.1\%$ w/w dw). Phenolics were present at low concentrations. PUFA levels were low, but halogenated metabolites, notably bromoform, were confirmed. These results indicate that proteins and polysaccharides are primary valorization targets, with halogenated compounds providing additional antimicrobial and methane mitigation potential.

Conclusion: *Asparagopsis armata* shows promising valorization potential: (i) proteins as nutritional supplements in aquafeeds, (ii) polysaccharides as functional hydrocolloids for food and cosmeceutical applications, and (iii) halogenated metabolites as bioactives with antimicrobial and environmental benefits. Integrating sustainable extraction and formulation strategies could transform *A. armata* from an invasive burden into a source of high-value bioproducts.

Keywords: *Asparagopsis armata*, Marine bioactives, Proteins, Polysaccharides, Halogenated metabolites

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